

Stakeholder perceptions of the most frequently used agroecological method of weed control in perennial crops (vineyards) in Steppic Region (Romania)

PROBLEM

What are the most common and effective agroecological methods for weed control in perennial crops in the Steppic Region?

STAKEHOLDER PERCEPTIONS

Farmers rely mainly on tillage, live mulches and cover crops. Although known, the Swiss Sandwich system and inert mulches are rarely used, along with thermal control and weed maps respectively. The parties concerned use extensive tillage, mowing, mulching and grazing, with intercropping also well known. Biological weed control is more common in vineyards, largely due to the added value of wine and the ecological trend. Manual weeding and manual hoeing are known for soil maintenance, encouraged by the trend of ecology but increasing production costs and the need for additional labour, a scarce resource. Bioherbicides, although widely known, have produced limited results, causing farmers to doubt their effectiveness.

Figure 1: Conventional Vineyard in Murfatlar, Romania

Figure 2: Conventional Vineyard in Murfatlar, Romania

RECOMMENDATION

Agroecological management of weeds in vineyards should focus on increasing biological control that is effective and sustainable. Expanding the use of mechanical control such as tillage and mulching combined with newer methods such as thermal weed control should be a priority. Farmers should explore innovative techniques with systematic integration of grazing, intercropping and cover crops. Education and research are essential to address gaps and adopt diverse weed management strategies suited to regional conditions.

Fig. 3: Organic Wine produced in Murfatlar, Romania

KEYWORDS

weed control in vineyards, agroecology in vineyards, viticulture, organic wine, integrated weed control.

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